

Intelligent Day-Ahead Scheduling for Distribution Networks With High Penetration of Distributed Renewable Energy Sources

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Abstract—In order to help Distribution System Operators (DSO) effectively manage their distribution networks with a high penetration of Distributed Renewable Energy Sources (DRES), this work proposes a day-ahead scheduling algorithm that takes into account the forecasts of DRES generation and loads, and intelligently utilizes flexibilities available in the network. The result is an optimal day-ahead schedule, which depending on the accuracy of the forecasts, will provide a means for DSOs to operate their network with the lowest operating expenditures. This proposed algorithm is validated on two test grids.

Index Terms—Distributed Generation, Optimization, Power Distribution, Smart Grids

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of unidirectional power delivery, which is as old as the power system itself, is ceasing to be true in many distribution networks today. This is due to a massive integration of Distributed Renewable Energy Sources (DRES) into these networks, causing local production and consumption of power, and sometimes even leading to power being fed back to transmission networks. These reverse flows present a great challenge for Distribution System Operators (DSO) who can no longer afford to control and supervise their networks in a too passive, or reactive manner. Indeed, there is a need for them to evolve and take into account the new possibilities brought about by the integration of more advanced communication and control systems, in managing their networks. Most distribution network optimization methods have considered the network conditions to be static, providing an optimal solution for only a “snapshot” of the network [1]. Different research studies have considered multi-temporal optimization [2]–[10], but have either not considered flexibilities like reconfiguration, which are available for exploitation, or have assumed for example that distributed generators are dispatchable in nature.

This work considers many available flexibilities, including reconfiguration, and also the effect that network manipulations done at one point of time during the day have on subsequent network conditions. It makes use of a dynamic programming based approach, and associates costs to DSO’s actions to achieve results.

II. THE ALGORITHM

As mentioned earlier, the algorithm uses a dynamic-programming based approach for optimization. It consists of two parts. The first is a reactive part, designed to react to network congestions (voltage and current) for the particular time interval where they occur. The second is an anticipative part, which strives to eliminate not only the congestions for the particular time interval, but also the congestions that might occur later due to its actions at one point of time. The choice between these two parts, based on the severity and scale of congestions, provides different results. In this work, congestions occurring in a single feeder are solved by the reactive part, while the anticipative part solves for network congestions occurring across feeders.

A. Cost Association for Network Activities

For the algorithm to work properly, costs have to be associated with each of the network conditions, and network actions taken by the DSO. This provides a common platform for analyzing solutions with network congestions in mind. Table I presents the costs associated to various such parameters as they were considered in this work.

TABLE I
MONETARY VALORIZATION OF NETWORK ACTIVITIES

Parameter	Monetary Value
Switching Operation	300 €
Load Reduction	6 €/MWh
OLTC Operation	20 €/Tap Change
Volt-VAr Control	132.9 €/MVArh
Voltage and Current Violations	500 €/Violation

B. Components and Working

Fig. 1 shows the general synoptic of the developed algorithm. The reactive *local optimization* routine and the anticipative *global optimization* routine perform their optimization tasks as explained, while the main program takes care of loading variables, data, and provides an output. The reconfiguration block is used to determine the best network configuration for a given network condition, and is based on a modified version of the algorithm described in [11]. A load-flow routine, developed in-house, is at the core of the algorithm. Network

reconfiguration decisions are based on the findings of the research in [12].

Fig. 1. The components of the algorithm

The main innovation brought about by the algorithm involve the *global optimization* routine, the detailed working of which will be explained in detail in the final paper. The consideration of DSO expenditures as the single most important objective, thereby providing a solution that will interest the DSOs the most.

III. TEST NETWORKS

Two networks are used for simulation-testing the algorithm. The first one, called the PREDIS network [13], is a test network constructed at University of Grenoble Alpes, representing a real distribution network at a reduced scale. It is a 14-bus, 17-line network with a connected load of 26.5 MVA and connected DRES of 27 MVA. It has three feeders, each equipped with its own On-Load Tap Changing (OLTC) Transformer. This network is shown in Fig. 2. DRES can be connected to all nodes in the network except nodes 1, 2, 3, 6, 8, and 11.

Fig. 2. The PREDIS Network

The second network is a 11-kV IEEE 70-bus rural test network with 79 lines, and a connected load of 5.41 MVA. Since no DRES information is available for this network,

it was conceived manually. More details on these networks, along with schematic representation of the second network will be presented in the final paper.

IV. RESULTS

Some of the results obtained by applying the developed multi-temporal operational planning tool on the PREDIS network are presented in the subsection below. We chose to present only the results for one load model and one DRES model, among others. The final paper will carry the results for other load and DRES models, and a detailed analysis of the results' dependency on various parameters.

A. Load and DRES Curves

Fig. 3 shows the load and DRES curves used in order to test the network. The curves are a cumulative representation of the loads and DRES at various nodes in the network during a period of 24 hours.

Fig. 3. Load and DRES Curves for PREDIS

It can be seen that during some times in the day, DRES penetration is over 80%. The cumulative load profiles are based on the work presented in [3].

B. Test Results

The following test results were obtained for the curves shown in Fig. 3. The hypothesis is that each node participates in load reduction of up to 10%, and each DRES connected can absorb up to 35% and produce up to 45% of its active power value in reactive power. Fig. 4 shows the reduction in losses in the PREDIS network when the proposed operational tool is applied. The cumulative energy loss in the network is reduced from 10 283 kWh to 3 773 kWh.

The minimum voltages in the network show a great improvement, as shown in Fig. 5. The minimum voltage remains above 0.95 pu for 21 of the 24 hours. It has to be compared to the minimum voltages in the original network, which are almost always below 0.95 pu.

The number of current and voltage violations in the network are decreased from 66 to 11 for the day under consideration. The various network actions suggested by the tool, along with the costs incurred, are summarized in Table II

Fig. 4. Network Loss Reduction

Fig. 5. Network Voltage Profiles

TABLE II
ALGORITHM OUTPUT

Money Spent without Optimization	34 364 €
Money Spent with Optimization	9 628 €
Load Reduced	1 315.50 kWh
Energy Supplied by DRES (VVC)	2 770.01 kVArh
Switching Operations (Reconfigurations)	18 (3)
OLTC Operations	3

V. CONCLUSIONS

A day-ahead dynamic-programming based algorithm was developed, with an ability to perform multi-temporal optimization as compared to optimizing for just a “snapshot” of networks, through the utilization of various flexibilities present in them. The algorithm also considers the effect of network manipulations during one time on the network conditions at a subsequent time.

By associating costs to network conditions and DSO actions, it is assured that the solution that the algorithm chooses for a particular network will be the solution that provides the lowest operating cost for that network, a point of interest for DSOs. The algorithm was then tested on two test networks and the results show a significant improvement in network conditions especially through losses, voltage profiles, and congestions.

Results for varied DRES and loads, along with an analysis of the influence of various parameters on the results, will be presented in the final paper.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Zidan and E. F. El-Saadany, “Network reconfiguration in balanced distribution systems with variable load demand and variable renewable resources generation,” in *IEEE PES General Meeting*, San Diego, Calif., Jul. 2012, pp. 1–8.
- [2] E. López, H. Opazo, L. García, and P. Bastard, “Online reconfiguration considering variability demand: Applications to real networks,” *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 549–553, 2004.
- [3] S.-A. Yin and C.-N. Lu, “Distribution feeder scheduling considering variable load profile and outage costs,” *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 652–660, 2009.
- [4] L. M. O. Queiroz and C. Lyra, “Adaptive hybrid genetic algorithm for technical loss reduction in distribution networks under variable demands,” *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 445–453, 2009.
- [5] R. S. Rao, K. Ravindra, K. Satish, and S. V. L. Narasimham, “Power loss minimization in distribution system using network reconfiguration in the presence of distributed generation,” *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 317–325, 2013.
- [6] J. Olamaei, T. Niknam, and G. Gharehpetian, “Application of particle swarm optimization for distribution feeder reconfiguration considering distributed generators,” *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 201, pp. 575–586, 2008.
- [7] S.-Y. Su, C.-N. Lu, R.-F. Chang, and G. Gutierrez-Alcaraz, “Distributed generation interconnection planning: A wind power case study,” *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 181–189, 2011.
- [8] R. Palma-Behnke, A. J.L.C., L. S. Vargas, and A. Jofre, “A distribution company energy acquisition market model with integration of distributed generation and load curtailment options,” *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 1718–1727, 2005.
- [9] H. Li, Y. Li, and Z. Li, “A multiperiod energy acquisition model for a distribution company with distributed generation and interruptible load,” *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 588–596, 2007.
- [10] A. Borghetti *et al.*, “Short-term scheduling and control of active distribution systems with high penetration of renewable resources,” *IEEE Sys. J.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 313–322, 2010.
- [11] D. Das, “A fuzzy multiobjective approach for network reconfiguration of distribution systems,” *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 202–209, 2006.
- [12] E. A. Bueno, C. Lyra, and C. Cavellucci, “Distribution network reconfiguration for loss reduction with variable demands,” in *Proc. 2004 IEEE PES T&D-LA*, Nov. 2004, pp. 384–389.
- [13] L. Le-Thanh, R. Caire, B. Raison, S. Bacha, and F. Blanche, “Test bench for self-healing functionalities applied on distribution network with distributed generators,” in *IEEE PowerTech*, Bucharest, Romania, Jun. 2009, pp. 1–6.
- [14] The evolVDSO website. [Online]. Available: <http://www.evolVDSO.eu>